

Effectiveness of Autogenic Drainage on airway clearance among patients with Bronchitis admitted at selected hospitals

Ms. Minal Sunil Jadhav ¹ Mrs. Swati Gorad ²

1. Speciality Medical Surgical Nursing, Sinhgad college of nursing
2. Designation Lecturer, Sinhgad college of nursing

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ABSTRACT: -

INTRODUCTION: This study investigates the effectiveness of autogenic drainage on airway clearance among patients with Bronchitis admitted at selected hospitals.

METHOD: - Research design adopted for the present study was Quasi experimental, non-randomized, pre-test post-test control group design. Quasi experimental research design involves the manipulation of independent variable to observe the effect of dependent variable, but it lacks at least one of the two characteristics of the true experimental design: randomized or a control group. The non-randomized control group design was used to assess the effect of autogenic drainage on airway clearance among patients with Bronchitis admitted at selected hospitals. It provides best framework for the study.

RESULT: -

The study encompassed a total of 60 sample from selected hospitals. With in detailed analysis of age, gender, occupational status, personal habits, frequency of nebulization, and chest physiotherapy. Significant improvement was observed in the experimental group, with a notable increase in airway clearance. Findings were recorded according to the tool. The data was gathered using descriptive and inferential statistics. The Fisher's exact test was used to find association between common associated risk factors with selected demographic variables.

CONCLUSION: -

The finding suggests that through Autogenic drainage helped in the airway clearance among patients with Bronchitis admitted at selected hospitals.

KEY WORDS: Autogenic Drainage, airway clearance, bronchitis

INTRODUCTION: -

The network of organs and tissues that facilitates breathing is known as the human respiratory system. The chemical activity that keeps the body's cells in a state of equilibrium requires energy. The majority of this energy comes from chemical reactions, which are only possible when oxygen (O₂) is present. Carbon dioxide (CO₂) is the primary waste product of these processes. The respiratory system provides the pathway for carbon dioxide excretion as well as the pathway for oxygen from the surrounding air to enter the body. When the bronchial tubes, which transport air to the lungs, become bloated and inflamed, it is known as bronchitis.¹

Jean Chevallier created the autogenic drainage breathing technique in 1967 in Belgium. Its goal is to gradually increase expiratory flows to transfer secretions from peripheral to central airways without the need for forced expirations and the resulting closure of airways. By starting with the tiny airways and transferring secretions from them to the bigger airways in three stages—unsticking, collection, and evacuation—autogenic drainage maximizes expiratory flow with the least amount of airway closure. By using expiratory muscles to control airflow and velocity and eliminating needless expiratory resistance, the patient transfers the mucus with a comfortable sighing exhale. The expiration is not forced to ensure optimal airflow. It has been proposed that autogenic drainage may offer secretion clearance. The goal of deep breathing exercises, also known as thoracic expansion exercises, is to raise lung volumes and force as much air as possible into the lungs to help shift any secretions (phlegm) that may be in the bottom of the lungs. In addition to mobilizing secretions, it helps all respiratory patients improve lung function and avoid atelectasis.²

NEED OF THE STUDY

Comparable rates of acute bronchitis were also found in a UK investigation, with an incidence of 54 occurrences per 1000 people. Interestingly, there is variation in these rates between age groups as well: rates are higher in those over 85 (225 per 1000) and lower in younger males (36 per 1000). Variations in healthcare-seeking behaviour, age-related immune responses, and exposure to viral infections in various environments could all be contributing factors to these disparities in occurrence. Additionally, several risk factors, such as a history of smoking, living in a polluted location, having a crowded home, and having previously had asthma, might lead to the development of acute bronchitis. Certain allergens, such as fumes, scents, and pollen, may cause acute bronchitis in those who are vulnerable.³

With India accounting for 11% of its non-communicable disease-related mortality, chronic respiratory disorders are becoming a growing source of worry for public health. Asthma and chronic bronchitis have significant morbidity rates. Autogenic drainage can promote self-management and empowerment, enabling patients to take an active role in their care. Effective airway clearance can potentially reduce the frequency of severity of exacerbations in Bronchitis, improving overall quality of life as it is a non-invasive method, making it a suitable option for patients who may have difficulty with more aggressive techniques.⁴

AIM OF STUDY: -

The study aims to Effectiveness of Autogenic Drainage on airway clearance among patients with Bronchitis admitted at selected hospitals.

METHODOLOGY: -

Study Design: The research design adopted for the present study is **Quasi experimental, non-randomized, pre-test post-test control group design**. Design to rigorously examine the Effectiveness of Autogenic drainage on airway clearance among patients with Bronchitis admitted at selected hospitals.

Inclusion criteria: Patients who are

1. Diagnosed with Bronchitis
2. Between the age group 30-55 years
3. Capable to follow verbal and written commands

Exclusion criteria:

1. Restrictive lung disease (tuberculosis and empyema)
2. Thoracic surgery
3. Emphysematous cavity
4. Head injury
5. Multiple respiratory and cardiac diseases.

Study instrument/ data collection tool:

Researcher will be using following tool

Section A - Consent form.

Section B: Structured Interviewing Questionnaire was prepared by the investigator, which includes questions regarding demographic variables: Age, Gender, Occupation, Personal Habits, and Frequency of nebulization

Section C: A table of selected respiratory parameters to assess the values on the 0 & 14th day of the intervention of Autogenic Drainage.

Description of intervention:

Place yourself in a comfortable sitting position with your neck slightly stretched to initiate autogenic drainage (AD). To get rid of mucus in your upper airways, blow your nose and cough hard. There are three stages to this method.

Steps:

Place yourself in a comfortable sitting position with your neck slightly stretched to initiate autogenic drainage (AD). To get rid of mucus in your upper airways, blow your nose and cough hard. There are three stages to this method.²

PHASE I: (Unsticking Phase) - Moving the mucus from the small airway

Start by controlling your breathing: inhale and exhale.

Relax.

Breathe deeply, then exhale completely until you feel as though your lungs are empty.

Take a tiny breath via your nose once your lungs are empty.

After holding the breath for three seconds, release the entire contents of the breath.

Do this two times.

PHASE II: (Collecting Phase)- Moving mucus from the small airways to the medium-sized airways.

Inhale normally sized breaths.

For three seconds, hold your breath.

Exhale all the air from your lungs using a moderate amount of force. You might feel like coughing but resist the urge to cough until the very end.

Repeat three times

PHASE III: (Evacuating Phase)- Moving mucus from the medium-sized airways to the large airways to be coughed out

Inhale deeply.

Maintain the grip for three seconds.

Exhale all the air from your lungs gently.

Repeat thrice

Coughing should wait until after the third breath.

Two to three minutes should be allotted for each phase. It should take six to nine minutes to finish one cycle, which consists of all three steps. This should take 20 to 45 minutes or until you have cleansed your lungs as much as possible. Repeat the cycle.²

Duration:

The Autogenic Drainage will be performed for 9 minutes; each cycle will be performed for 3 minutes.

The 9-minute cycle conducted twice a day.

Statistical Analysis:

In this study, descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation, frequency distribution) summarized baseline characteristics. Inferential statistics (paired t-tests, two-sample t-tests, Fisher's exact test) were

used to analyse within-group and between-group differences, assessing the significance of observed changes.

Ethical Considerations:

Institutional Review Board (IRB): Approval is sought from the relevant ethical review board. Participants are fully briefed on the study, and written consent is obtained, ensuring compliance with ethical standards.

RESULT:

In the experimental group, in the pretest, 16.7% of the patients with bronchitis had a moderately cleared airway, 46.7% of them had a minimally cleared airway, and 36.7% of them had a very minimally cleared airway. In the posttest, 13.3% of the patients with bronchitis had a well-cleared airway, 36.7% of them had a moderately cleared airway, and 50% of them had a very minimally cleared airway. In the control group, in the pretest, 20% of the patients with bronchitis had a moderately cleared airway, 43.3% of them had a minimally cleared airway, and 36.7% of them had a very minimally cleared airway. In the posttest, 23.3% of the patients with bronchitis had moderately cleared airway, 63.3% of them had minimally cleared airway, and 13.3% of them had very minimally cleared airway. This indicates that there is a remarkable improvement in airway clearance among patients with bronchitis in the experimental group.

Table 3.1: Airway clearance among patients with Bronchitis after implementation of autogenic drainage

n=30, 30

Airway clearance	Experimental				Control			
	Pretest		Posttest		Pretest		Posttest	
	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%
Well cleared	0	0.0%	4	13.3%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%
Moderately cleared	5	16.7%	11	36.7%	6	20.0%	7	23.3%
Minimally cleared	14	46.7%	15	50.0%	13	43.3%	19	63.3%
Very minimally cleared	11	36.7%	0	0.0%	11	36.7%	4	13.3%

Figure no: 4.8 Bar diagram showing the percentage-wise distribution of airway clearance among patients with Bronchitis after implementation of autogenic drainage

Analysis of data related to the association between airway clearance and selected demographic variables

Fisher's exact test for association between airway clearance and selected demographic variables

Since p-values corresponding to the frequency of nebulization and chest physiotherapy were small (less than 0.05), the demographic variables frequency of nebulization and chest physiotherapy were found to have significant association with the airway clearance among patients with bronchitis.

DISCUSSION:

The study aimed to investigate the Effectiveness of Autogenic drainage on airway clearance among patients with Bronchitis admitted at selected hospitals.

Present study demonstrated significant improvement was observed in the experimental group, with a notable increase in airway clearance among patients with Bronchitis.

This prompted the implementation of the Autogenic Drainage. Post-test outcomes revealed significant progress, 13.3% of the patients with bronchitis had a well-cleared airway, 36.7% of them had a moderately cleared airway, and 50% of them had a very minimally cleared airway. In the control

group, in the pretest, 20% of the patients with bronchitis had a moderately cleared airway, 43.3% of them had a minimally cleared airway, and 36.7% of them had a very minimally cleared airway. In the post-test, 23.3% of the patients with bronchitis had moderately cleared airway, 63.3% of them had minimally cleared airway, and 13.3% of them had very minimally cleared airway. This improvement was strongly supported by statistical analysis, including the rejection of the null hypothesis through paired t-test analysis. The average reduction in airway clearance score in the experimental group was 3.4, which was 1 in the control group. The Z-value for this test was 8.9. The corresponding p-value was small (less than 0.05), and the null hypothesis was rejected. The average reduction in airway clearance in the experimental group is significantly more than that in the control group. It is evident that autogenic drainage is significantly effective in improving airway clearance among patients with bronchitis. The t-value for this test was 16.9, with 29 degrees of freedom. The corresponding p-value was small (less than 0.05) So the study was effective.

CONCLUSION:

In conclusion, this study demonstrates the significant This research adopts a non-randomized pre-test post-test control group design to rigorously examine the Effectiveness of Autogenic drainage on airway clearance among patients with Bronchitis admitted at selected hospitals. The study encompasses patients with Bronchitis admitted at selected hospitals.

The finding suggests that Autogenic drainage helped in airway clearance among patients with Bronchitis.

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